

Students' Interest in Learning English at Iain Syekh Nurjati Cirebon: Study of Instrumental and Integrative Motivation

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ABSTRACT: Motivation is vital for learning and mastering a language. Motivation related to second language learning is integrative and instrumental motivation. This research aims to describe students' interest in learning English from the terms instrumental and integrative motivation. The research design is quantitative descriptive. The information obtained is interpreted as tables, diagrams and sentences. The research location is at the IAIN Syekh Nurjati Cirebon campus for the odd academic year 2023-2024. The sample size was 100 students studying English using simple random sampling techniques. Data collection tools are questionnaires related to instrumental and integrative motivation, with 20 statements. The results show that integrative motivation is higher than instrumental motivation for various reasons. The instrumental motivation of students' desire to study English leads to the conclusion that their motivation is tied to their employment, future profession, and education. Regarding integration motivation, they recognized that English is a crucial language for worldwide communication. They are also eager to visit English-speaking countries, engage with native speakers, and utilize English with English-speaking friends or acquaintances. The majority of students learn English because of integrative motivation.

KEYWORDS: motivation, instrumental, integrative, learning, English

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning is a series of actions that modify the behaviour of the learning topic (Lin et al., 2003; Kuswanda et al., 2020). This behavioural shift can manifest itself in a variety of ways, including the learning topic becoming more creative. Several aspects define creativity in learning, including open thinking, spontaneity, curiosity, and independence. Creativity in learning does not come out of nowhere; a variety of internal and external circumstances impact it. If a person is willing to learn, he will be successful and innovative. Motivation refers to the desire or impulse to study something.

Students who are motivated to study experience a shift in their inner energy (Brooks et al., 2012). The impulse that originates within a person transforms into energy that drives them to work or study, seek out and solve difficulties until they are resolved. Motivated students also behave in ways that lead them to achieve their goals (Huriyah et al., 2022; Pratomo, 2022; Anditasari et al., 2023).

Higher education, as an educational institution, is responsible for offering excellent education in order to generate graduates who are highly competitive and capable of meeting the demands of the times. Quality education is becoming increasingly important as science and technology advance. The ideal institution delivers high-quality and competitive education, with all systems functioning well.

In Indonesia, learning English is done both through formal and non-formal institutions. In formal institutions, students have studied English since elementary school level, but it can still be said to be inadequate. Several findings in the field show this, such as students' low English scores on national exams and the low frequency of English use among students.

The types of motivation in learning are extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation (Lin et al., 2003; Shaikholeslami et al., 2006; Pratomo et al., 2022; Fatimah et al., 2022). Extrinsic motivation is a learning activity that grows from a person's encouragement and needs that are not absolutely related to their learning activities (Brophy, 2004). Intrinsic motivation is a learning activity initiated and continued based on the appreciation of a need and drive that is absolutely related to the learning activity (Cameron et al., 2002).

According to Gardner et al. (1972), motivation related to second language learning is integrative and instrumental function motivation. Motivation has an integrative function if the motivation encourages someone to learn a language because of the desire to communicate with the community that speaks that language or become a member of that language community. Meanwhile, motivation has an instrumental function if it encourages someone to have the desire to learn a second language for a helpful purpose or because of the urge to obtain a job or social mobility at the top of society.

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Efforts to raise students' learning motivation are by clarifying the goals to be achieved, arousing students' interest, creating a pleasant atmosphere in learning, giving reasonable praise for each student's success, giving assessments, giving comments on the results of student's work, and create competition and cooperation that can have a good influence on the success of the student learning process (Brophy, 2004).

Gardner et al. (1959) stated that integrative motivation is more important than instrumental motivation. However, research by Gardner and Lambert (1959) proved that there was no significant relationship between integrative motivation and language mastery. Chihara et al. (1978) stated that there was little correlation between attitudes and language skills. Meanwhile, Kholid (2017) stated that instrumental motivation plays a more critical role than integrative motivation. This research aims to describe interest in learning English from the terms Instrumental and Integrative motivation.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The research design is quantitative descriptive (Djubaedi et al., 2023). The information obtained is interpreted in the form of tables, diagrams and sentences. The research location is at the IAIN Syekh Nurjati Cirebon campus for the odd academic year 2023-2024. The sample size was 100 students studying English using simple random sampling techniques (Sutisno et al., 2023). Data collection tools are questionnaires related with instrumental motivation and integrative motivation. Each statement indicator is 10, with a total of 20 statements that have been tested for validity and reliability. The following is a description of the questionnaire indicators and the results of the validity and reliability tests.

Instrumental motivation indicator on the statement (Muktianingsih et al., 2021): 1) I only use English to complete assignments from lecturers and exams. 2) In class, I tend to rely on textbooks and have difficulty expressing myself well. 3) I only read English books related to university studies, but don't read anything else, for example, magazines and so on. 4) I am motivated to graduate from college and get a good job rather than focus on learning English. 5) I am more motivated to continue my education to a higher level rather than just focusing on learning English. 6) I need to Learn English to travel abroad. 7) Learning English is essential for me to gain experience and skills. 8) Learning English is vital to turn me into an educated person. 9) Being good at using English can lead to success and achievement. 10) Being good at English makes other people respect me.

Integrative motivation indicator on the statement (Muktianingsih et al., 2021): 1) Learning English improves your understanding of English songs, books, films, etc. 2) Learning English makes me understand and appreciate the way of life of people whose mother tongue is English. 3) Learning English gives me the opportunity to communicate with people abroad. 4) Learning English provides opportunities for discussions with people abroad. 5) Through learning English provides the opportunity to transfer knowledge to foreigners. 6) Learning English provides opportunities to participate with other cultural groups through academic, professional, and cultural activities. 7) Learning English provides an opportunity to imitate the behaviour of people whose mother tongue is English. 8) Learning English provides an opportunity to appreciate English literature and art. 9) Learning English gives me the opportunity to be open-minded. 10) I have a strong desire to learn English to the fullest.

Validity tests were carried out on 20 respondents. Based on the r Product Moment table on sig. 0.05, $r = 0.444$. If the r value calculated using SPSS is greater than 0.444, then it can be said that the statement is valid.

Table 1. Instrument Validity Test Results

Item Statements	r count use SPSS	Criteria	
		Valid	Invalid
Instrumental Motivation			
1	0.802	√	
2	0.914	√	
3	0.761	√	
4	0.698	√	
5	0.801	√	
6	0.842	√	
7	0.733	√	
8	0.872	√	
9	0.842	√	
10	0.740	√	
Integrative instrumental			
1	0.820	√	
2	0.837	√	
3	0.916	√	
4	0.814	√	
5	0.769	√	

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6	0.876	√	
7	0.775	√	
8	0.843	√	
9	0.812	√	
10	0,793	√	

Based on Table 1, it is known that ten instrumental motivation statements are valid, and ten integral motivation statements are valid. Therefore, this instrument is suitable for use in this survey.

The reliability test for instrumental motivation and integral motivation uses the Alpha Cronbach formula with the help of SPSS. Based on calculations with the help of SPSS software, the Cronbach's Alpha value (Fuad, 2023) for the reliability of the instrument is 0.933. Based on reliability criteria, it is included in the very reliable category, meaning that the instrument is suitable for use in this survey.

Analysis of the questionnaire results is based on Likert scale values from 1 to 5 (Nasir et al., 2022), then interpreted based on the average value in table 2 below.

Table 2. Interpretation of mean values

Mean Range	Interpretation of Motivation
3.68 – 5.00	High
2.34 – 3.67	Moderate
1.00 – 2.33	Low

Sources: (Wimolmas, 2013)

III. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

A. Results

Table 3 below shows the average respondents' answers based on categories for instrumental motivation.

Table 3. Results of Instrumental Motivation

Indicator Instrumental Motivation on the Statement	Mean	Categories		
		Low	Moderate	High
I only use English to complete assignments from lecturers and exams	3.88			√
In class, I tend to rely on textbooks and have difficulty expressing myself well.	2.89		√	
I only read English books related to university studies, but don't read anything else, for example, magazines and so on.	2.26	√		
I am motivated to graduate from college and get a good job rather than focus on learning English	2.92		√	
I am more motivated to continue my education to a higher level rather than just focusing on learning English.	2.72		√	
I need to Learn English to travel abroad.	3.64		√	
Learning English is essential for me to gain experience and skills.	4.42			√
Learning English is vital to turn me into an educated person	3.24		√	
Being good at using English can lead to success and achievement.	4.28			√
Being good at English makes other people respect me.	3.82			√
Average	3.407		√	

Table 3 shows that respondents have instrumental motivation in the medium category, with an average score of 3.407. The statement "Learning English is essential for me to gain experience and skills" has the highest average score in the high category, namely 4.42. The statement "I need to Learn English to travel abroad." has the highest average score in the moderate category, namely 3.64. In instrumental motivation, there is the lowest mean value, namely 2.89, with the statement, "I only read English

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books related to university studies, but don't read anything else, for example, magazines and so on.". However, overall, the average score for instrumental motivation shows a moderate motivation category.

Table 4 below shows the average respondents' answers based on categories for integrative motivation

Table 4. Results of Integrative Motivation

Indicator Instrumental Integrative on the Statement	Mean	categories		
		Low	Moderate	High
Learning English improves your understanding of English songs, books, films, etc.	4.50			√
Learning English makes me understand and appreciate the way of life of people whose mother tongue is English.	4.23			√
Learning English gives me the opportunity to communicate with people abroad.	4.06			√
Learning English provides opportunities for discussions with people abroad.	4.23			√
Through learning English provides the opportunity to transfer knowledge to foreigners.	4.43			√
Learning English provides opportunities to participate with other cultural groups through academic, professional, and cultural activities.	4.02			√
Learning English provides an opportunity to imitate the behaviour of people whose mother tongue is English.	4.21			√
Learning English provides an opportunity to appreciate English literature and art.	4.10			√
Learning English gives me the opportunity to be open-minded.	4.32			√
I have a strong desire to learn English to the fullest.	4.14			√
Average	4.224			√

Table 4 shows that respondents have integrative motivation in the high category, seen with an average score of 4.224. The statement "Learning English improves your understanding of English songs, books, films, etc." has the highest average score in the high category, namely 4.50. Meanwhile, the statement "Learning English provides opportunities to participate with other cultural groups through academic, professional, and cultural activities." has the lowest average score in the high category, namely 4.02. However, overall, the average score of integrative motivation shows a high motivation category.

Students' Dominant Motivation

Figure 1 below shows the results of the analysis of the types of student motivation for learning English

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Figure 1 shows the results of an analysis of the types of student motivation in learning English at IAIN Syekh Nurjati Cirebon, which was conducted by a survey of 100 students. There were 82 students, or 82%, who had integrative motivation, and 18 students, or 18%, were motivated by instrumental motivation. These findings demonstrate that the majority of students learn English because to integrative motivation.

B. Discussion

Motivation is essential in learning and mastering a language. English teachers work hard to encourage and engage students in the use of the language during and beyond the teaching-learning situation (Rathiga et al., 2019). Learning a second language is extremely important because it allows you to communicate with individuals from various cultures. The results and evidence analysis show that students are motivated to learn English. Based on the result of instrumental motivation, shows that students' motivation is in the medium category, with an average score of 3.407. Based on the result of integrative motivation, shows that students' motivation in the high category is seen with an average score of 4.224. The study indicated that students have a somewhat stronger integrative motivation to learn English, addressing the question of whether motivation is primarily instrumental or integrative.

These findings supported by Dörnyei (1990), who discovered that instrumental motivation may be more critical than integrative motivation for foreign language learners because they are unlikely to have sufficient knowledge and experience to participate in the culture of the people who speak the target language in their early stages of language learning. However, this finding contradicts with study of Zanghar (2012), which found that students exhibited both instrumental and integrative drive to study English, with integrative motivation slightly stronger than instrumental motivation. Kato (2016) believes that students might improve and act on their integrative drive while in their native country.

The results of the data analysis on integrative motivation above show that students' desire to interact with English culture, literature, and history must be increased because integrative motivation is an essential component of successful language learning. This is consistent with Hernández (2006), who noted that integrative motivation, which focuses on enhancing the student's language competency, may be improved by offering the students additional opportunities to connect with native speakers and study abroad. He also emphasized the need to use natural language in conversational contexts. Martinsen (2010) suggested that cultural awareness can help pupils enhance their language abilities. Furthermore, Samad et al. (2012) stated that English teachers should become more aware of affective factors such as integrative motivation because teachers who are aware of motivation can help students promote their integrative motivation by providing opportunities for them to communicate and interact within a language community.

CONCLUSIONS

The majority of students learn English because to integrative motivation. The research results show that integrative motivation is higher than instrumental motivation for various reasons. Generally, the study's findings indicate that students are motivated to learn English for integrative and instrumental reasons. In terms of integration, they recognized that English is a crucial language for worldwide communication. They are also eager to visit English-speaking countries, engage with native speakers, and utilize English with English-speaking friends or acquaintances. These activities will provide relevant opportunities to utilize the language and investigate the linguistic and cultural characteristics of the English culture. Using multimedia such as the internet, mobile phone applications, radio, or TV broadcasts can provide an interactive learning experience.

The instrumental motivation of students' desire to study English leads to the conclusion that their motivation is tied to their employment, future profession, and education. As a result, it is proposed that the English instructor give additional opportunities for pupils to improve their English skills in preparation for future professions and occupations. Providing students with real-life workplace communications and demands will help them prepare for the job market.

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